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Renewable and Sustainable Energy Transition

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Promoting sustainable transitions across the globe requires scenario co-creation with key stakeholders

The Paris Agreement rests on individual countries and regions identifying stretching but feasible mitigation pathways. These must be acceptable and achievable in the eyes of a range of stakeholders in those countries or regions, including those from civil society, governments, and businesses. This Special Issue explores a range of feasible yet ambitious greenhouse gas emissions reduction pathways in a diversity of regions/countries of the world, in principle compatible with the goals of the Paris Agreement on climate change. Each of these pathways have been developed using energy system models or whole-economy models, in most cases using mitigation scenarios co-created with a range of policy, civil society, academic, and business stakeholders.

Although the Paris Agreement established a global goal to constrain mean temperature increase to well-below 2°C, this goal will not be achieved unless every country and/or region in the world joins the effort, commits to ambitious mitigation actions, and follows through. Such actions, however, cannot succeed if they are imposed on society from above; instead, they must be designed and implemented bottom-up, with all stakeholders on board, to ensure societal buy-in, acceptance, and active engagement in the effort. In turn, modelling science tasked with informing climate policymaking must also be done collaboratively with a diversity of stakeholders, to enable this societal buy-in early on, to maximise real-world feasibility of model-derived insights from a societal perspective, as well as to improve model accuracy with inputs informed in consultations.

Developing and exploring stakeholder-driven scenarios is not new in modelling science, yet it remains relatively rare in the literature [1]. This is in part because such stakeholder interaction is difficult and resource-intensive, requiring organisational and educational effort to identify, attract, and inform stakeholders of the scenario co-creation process, interact with them meaningfully to extract information, and keep them interested and engaged throughout, while keeping balanced representation of the diversity of actors and addressing potential biases. Another reason could lie in the interests of the scientific world itself: with time to act for the climate crisis running out, scientists are more interested in the insights stemming from critical research questions rather than in the processes that motivated these research questions to begin with. At the same time, stakeholder participation can also be potentially risky in that it cannot guarantee that any consensus on which questions and assumptions to explore will be the most useful or scientifically salient from a scientific perspective, nor that any such useful consensus on how to reach ambitious mitigation targets will be achieved in the first place. Indeed, given the stringency of the targets and the requirements and implications for the stakeholders themselves, it could well be the case that there is pushback—or at least some

reluctance—from the engaged actors to even discuss pathways that ‘tick the Paris box’.

This is also why this Special Issue has paid significant attention to highlighting the benefits of and good practices for scenario co-creation for mitigation modelling. In particular, Wachsmuth et al. [5] presented evidence from a series of co-creation workshops in five countries (Brazil, Canada, Germany, Greece, and the United Kingdom), each with a different sectoral focus but all with the shared goal of identifying and discussing factors possibly hindering the realisation of modelled mitigation pathways and narrating tailored policy strategies to overcome these bottlenecks. Apart from showcasing the gap between the pathways stemming from strictly formalised model frameworks and the real-life context in which the end goals of these pathways should be achieved, this study foremost stressed common themes of concern across countries and sectors, including but not limited to regulatory instability, political pressures, and incumbency of fossil fuel (or other) industries. It also stressed common possible solutions, such as capital allocation towards massive low-carbon investments (including in critical enabling infrastructures), combination of technology push with demand pull measures, heavier focus on the demand side of the transition, and dialogues with stakeholders and citizens to set commonly agreed cornerstones of the required transformations. If anything, the latter also underpinned the value of dialogue in policy and science alike, as it was within such dialogues that stakeholders themselves saw the value in their engagement. In addition, they had the opportunity to uncover the divergence of their perceptions, motives, and strategies with scientific perspectives and policy expectations or other participating stakeholders’ interests. Most importantly, this research offered ways to meaningfully conduct stakeholder interactions that extend model-based pathways to socio-technical narratives, navigate course corrections/amendments to the modelling scenarios, and eventually lead to policy narratives that can act as facilitators of transformation.

In this context, this Special Issue was specifically designed to highlight a range of economy-wide and/or sectoral decarbonisation pathways, which have in many cases had significant co-creation aspects with stakeholders (e.g., in Greece, Canada, and the Russian Federation) within such facilitative environments as the ones produced by Wachsmuth et al. [5], spanning governments, businesses, academics, and civil society actors. A range of specific findings are notable.

For example, Karamaneas et al. [6] documented such a stakeholder-driven modelling process for Greece’s energy transition in the light of (the European and international policy responses to) the energy supply crisis that was fuelled by the Russia-Ukraine conflict in 2022. By coupling two energy system modelling frameworks, this

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research first assessed the evolution of Greek energy demand and electricity generation mix until 2035 in the context of Greece's now-outdated National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) and of the Climate Law, which was expected to reflect increased ambition to match the EU's net-zero targets and consideration of the bloc's REPowerEU strategy to limit its dependence on Russian gas. This research, however, showed that said legal framework would bring negligible emissions cuts to the table and, ironically, increase the role of natural gas in the country's electricity mix. It thus introduced an alternative way forward that is better aligned with long-term decarbonisation visions and near-term degasification objectives. Rather than involving local actors early to drive their original research questions, it is after using their integrated model framework that Karamaneas et al. [6] interacted with a diverse group of stakeholders to shed light on key uncertainties and bottlenecks that may prove critical to delivering on the climate mitigation agenda and yet were hidden from the modelling exercise: different paces of natural gas price recovery, community opposition to onshore wind expansion to the levels prescribed by the models, unavailability of geothermal power that would instead entail increased hydropower needs, and a stronger grip of the gas regime on Greek energy planning that could hamper investments in biomass and offshore wind. The updated model runs showed that, even if complete decarbonisation of the country's power sector would still be feasible, coming up with a national strategy that is robust against stakeholders' concerns would entail bolder supply-side diversification and costlier investments in a subset of existing or emerging technologies.

In a similar setting, Bailie et al. [4] used an energy model for Canada to explore the country's energy-system requirements and implications of moving from an emissions trajectory driven by the policies currently in place, to a more ambitious trajectory that is in line with both the 2030 target of Canada's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC) and the 2050 vision for net zero emissions. After unveiling these implications of a least-cost pathway to net zero by the middle of the century, Bailie et al. [4] then held a co-creation workshop that allowed a group of stakeholders to be informed and reflect on the modelled pathways, identify and discuss their concerns, and eventually help the research team to reflect these concerns within a revisited scenario design. In their research, Bailie et al. [4] endogenised into the model assumptions these concerns, which inter alia included uncertainties associated with carbon capture and storage technologies (potential, price volatility, at-scale availability, etc.), modal shifts and decarbonisation options outside passenger road transport, urban planning, building practices, and behavioural changes, as well as quantified the added value of stakeholder engagement: the revised scenario exercise stressed that the stakeholder-constrained possibility space towards net zero is becoming increasingly smaller, even if outcomes of the discussions with the stakeholders did not lead to fundamental changes to the scenario reconfiguration.

Contrary to this 'modelling-engagement-remodelling' research approach followed for Greece and Canada, Shirov et al. [7] instead interacted with a uniquely large group of stakeholders early in the process to co-design the model scenarios to begin with. Following a panel discussion and three breakout sessions dedicated to different sectors that are deemed critical in Russia's decarbonisation efforts (power, industry, forest), stakeholders were asked to co-create selected scenario specifications in a concluding voting session, in which they provided their perceptions over the ambition of a series of mitigation targets, their prioritisation of transition bottlenecks, and their assessment of technological risks. This process led to the design of two scenarios of different climate ambition, which were assessed in an input-output energy-economic model of interconnected macro-structural calculations at the national level. This stakeholder-informed modelling exercise highlighted the potential to realistically achieve net zero emissions in Russia around the middle of the century, without hampering long-term economic development, and the importance of a diversified portfolio of measures and technologies

that encompasses heavy investments in energy efficiency and intensity improvements (especially in mining and manufacturing industries) and electrification, as well as considerable expansion of and insistence on nuclear power as opposed to a relatively conservative expansion of renewables in the power sector. Moreover, increased forest management toward maximising the benefits from Russian ecosystem's carbon sinks and the fight against fugitive emissions from the extractive industry were identified as having notable potential to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions in Russia at moderate cost.

This collection has furthermore set out to consider geographical scales typically underrepresented in modelling science, such as New South Wales in Australia or the Eastern Mediterranean Middle East (EMME) region, as well as regions with unique, context-specific features that are also underexplored in the modelling literature, such as Indonesia.

Taliotis et al. [2] used an energy-system model to investigate the implications of decarbonisation on inter-regional electricity trade for the EMME region, bringing into the spotlight countries critical to global decarbonisation efforts and yet underrepresented in modelling literature, such as Turkey, Iran, or Saudi Arabia. They find that decarbonisation efforts would enhance regional integration requirements, in terms of coordination of interconnection infrastructure investment and storage deployment, so as to balance increasingly variable electricity supply—from weather-dependent low-carbon renewable electricity such as wind and solar—with electricity demand. Should such coordination foster economic cooperation more generally, to better tie both Eastern and Western Mediterranean nations together, as has happened in other regional cases (notably steel and coal unions that established the conditions for the EU in the post-war period), then there could be socio-political benefits beyond simply energy supply-demand balancing.

Narrowing down instead to the sub-national level, Murugesan et al. [3] used a national energy system model for Australia to examine how the state of New South Wales can align its policy framework with the country's net zero emissions ambition by 2050, while boosting regional energy affordability and security. The research defines a set of scenarios, one reflecting baseline targets and currently deployed policies, and a deep decarbonisation scenario reflecting increased ambition across a number of drivers, such as renewable energy deployment, energy efficiency improvements, activity growth, electrification, etc. Murugesan et al. [3] estimate that New South Wales could in fact achieve net zero emissions by as early as 2039, by pursuing complete power-sector decarbonisation, fostering an enabling environment for electric vehicle penetration (namely, a range of measures with regard to the conversion of the public vehicle fleet, tax exemptions, charging infrastructure), achieving high levels of electrification, imposing high-efficiency standards in residential and commercial buildings, and decarbonising hard-to-abate industries within a decade.

Finally, Shah et al. (2023) used a similar model framework to that used in the study of Greece's transition by Karamaneas et al. [6], in order to explore various long-term electricity planning strategies in Indonesia, with a view to reduce reliance on coal and other fossil fuels. In doing so, they touched upon important challenges and hurdles, including strong subsidies towards fossil fuels that distort the country's energy landscape, a hitherto limited role of the private sector for power generation, and chronic underfunding of the state utility company hampering its ability to invest in new technologies and infrastructure, as well as upon solutions such as green use of carbon tax revenues. Model results showed that the more ambitious scenarios underpin the realism of a moratorium on coal in the country, which however would reinforce the share of natural gas in the near-term apart from that of renewables; they also showed that a net zero pathway would lock the country heavily in solar power and associated imports, as the country itself has no domestic manufacturing capacity.

Given this context-specificity, there is little generalisability across the countries, sectors, and scenarios examined in the studies comprising the Special Issue, although some common features emerge from all seven

studies, including the big role of energy efficiency and electrification, the potential and limitations of carbon capture and storage, as well as the feasibility of deep decarbonisation targets themselves, which seemingly remain within grasp not only from a model solution perspective but also from the stakeholders' otherwise more constraining points of view. More importantly, studies with co-creation elements also highlighted the added value of participatory processes, especially as we enter a world of overlapping societal objectives that in turn require documenting and making use of the knowledge and strategies embedded in society itself, as well as of overlapping risks, thereby adding to the uncertainty spectrum and stressing the need for transdisciplinary insights to push science and policy forward.

It should, finally, be noted that this collection also had a strong focus on open-source modelling, notably with the development and use of different model implementations of the Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) to address questions relevant in different geographical contexts (Indonesia, Greece, and the EMME region), indicating that open science helps enable stakeholders' understanding of model assumptions and inner workings and supports scenario exercises in regions with limited domestic modelling capacity.

We hope that the collection provides insight and inspiration for further expanding the foresight toolkit from purely modelling approaches to those that also encompass the expertise and real-world knowledge of various stakeholders. Only through such participatory approaches are we likely to achieve feasible, just, and societally acceptable low-carbon transitions.

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